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*BR102019024232A2***(22) Deposit Date: 11/18/2019****(43) National Publication Date: 05/25/2021****(54) Title:** AUTOMATIC TREADMILL IN HYPERBARIC CHAMBER**(51) Int. Cl.:** A01K 1/03.**(52) CPC:** A01K 1/031**(71) Depositor(s):** FEDERAL INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY OF SANTA CATARINA; SANTA CATARINA STATE UNIVERSITY FOUNDATION.**(72) Inventor(s):** VALDIR NOLL; CYNTHIA BEATRIZ SCHEFFER DUTRA; HENRIQUE GHIZONTI; GUILHERME KLEGUES CIDADE; GUSTAVO RACHID DUTRA; NICOLAS MEDEIROS PACHECO; ANA MARIA NAVARRO BARBOSA; ARTHUR RAULINO KRETZER; ALAN DEIVIS VALMORBIDA; GABRIEL BULIGON DAL PONTE; ELITON PROBST; JHONATTAN GUTJAHR; DEBORAH DE CAMARGO HIZUME KUNZLER.**(57) Summary:** AUTOMATED TREADMILL IN HYPERBARIC CHAMBER. Automated treadmills, with speed control and inclination, start and end of exercise, specially designed for mice and rats, arranged inside a hyperbaric chamber, in order to perform ergometric tests, such as walking, running, inclined running, under various atmospheric pressures.

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AUTOMATIC TREADMILL IN HYPERBARIC CHAMBER

[1] The present invention is situated in the field of physics, more specifically testing instruments, exactly an automated treadmill, arranged in a hyperbaric chamber, to carry out ergometric tests, especially on mice or rats.

[2] Rats and mice are commonly used in a wide variety of research and scientific experiments aimed at improving and constantly seeking solutions to human health problems. One of these is to evaluate the effects of aerobic physical training (ATT) applied to animal models of chronic lung diseases, with the aim of studying these phenomena and their various possible remedies.

[3] An in-depth analysis of the state of the art reveals a gap in exercise treadmills arranged in hyperbaric chambers that allow physiological tests on mice or rats.

[4] In order to highlight these gaps, the analysis of document CN104885954, "The construction method for a rat hypoxia simulation model of a highland low-pressure hypoxia simulation chamber", requested by Jia Zhengping on April 7, 2015, provides a construction method for a simulation model of hypoxia in rats in a low-pressure chamber. The method comprises the following steps: firstly, carrying out treadmill tests on experimental rats and selecting hypoxia-sensitive rats by simulating an environment with an altitude of 3500 meters in the hypoxia simulation chamber; secondly, randomly selecting hypoxia-sensitive rats and placing the selected rats in the simulation chamber; thirdly, establishing conditions for the experimental simulation of hypoxia in rats; fourthly, identifying the biochemical indices of blood gases and the pathological indices of hypoxia-sensitive rats after hypoxia for 24-120h. The invention, unlike what is proposed, features a low-pressure chamber and does not offer an automated treadmill.

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[5] Furthermore, protection CN105165650, “Small animal autokinetic treadmill”, deposited by Tianjin University of Sport on August 7, 2015, discloses an autokinetic treadmill for small animals that is a new ecological breeding box for small animals. It comprises a roller support, a mouse box, a protective cover, rollers, a food basket, a lifting frame, a non-slip protective cover, a conveyor belt and the like, where the roller support, the rollers and the conveyor belt form the auto-kinetic belt, one lower end of the roller support is connected to the box by means of a rotating shaft, the other end of the roller support is supplied with the food basket and used to adjust angles of the auto-kinetic belt. The beneficial effects of the treadmill are that the ecological breeding box of autokinetic animal movement is developed with the help of the autokinetic treadmill concept, real and reliable physiological parameters of different amounts of exercise that can be obtained directly in a small animal breeding process for obtaining physiological parameters of exercise in scientific animal research. The treadmill in question is not arranged in a hyperbaric chamber.

[6] Finally, patent CN103999794, “Rat simulation weightless treadmill training method and rat simulation weightless treadmill”, by Scient Res Training Ct For Chinese Astronauts, filed on May 28, 2014, refers to a zero-gravity simulation treadmill training method for rats and a treadmill. The method comprises the steps of setting up a treadmill and allows the adjustment of an acute angle between the treadmill and the horizontal plane; fitting a deflector plate at one end of the conveyor belt and allowing the deflector plate to extend outwards from a fixed pulley support; allowing for a hole in the deflector plate; placing the rat on the conveyor belt with its tail oriented towards one end of the deflector plate, attaching the insulated end to the rat's tail and allowing a load-bearing piece to be attached to the other end of the insulated connecting part after the other end penetrates the passage hole of the deflector plate and occupies a groove of a fixed pulley. The method can meet the requirements of scientific research, especially manned spaceflight, and allows the zero-gravity environment to be simulated on the ground. The treadmill in question does not allow tests in a hyperbaric chamber.

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[7] The documents found in the analysis of the state of the art do not present automated treadmills, with speed and incline control, start and end of exercise, as is the case with treadmills for humans, specially designed for murines (mice and rats), arranged inside hyperbaric chambers, which can alter the internal pressure to be greater than the external pressure by up to 20 mmH₂O, in order to carry out ergometric tests, such as walking, running, incline running, under various atmospheric pressures, equipped with pressure, speed and incline control systems for the treadmill inside the chamber. The documents found in the analysis of the state of the art do not present automated treadmills, with speed and incline control, start and end of exercise, as is the case with treadmills for humans, specially designed for murines (mice and rats), arranged inside hyperbaric chambers, which can alter the internal pressure to be greater than the external pressure by up to 20 mmH₂O, in order to carry out ergometric tests, such as walking, running, incline running, under various atmospheric pressures, equipped with pressure, speed and incline control systems for the treadmill inside the chamber.

[8] A new arrangement is therefore proposed: a treadmill, consisting of a tarpaulin (1), two rollers (4) that pull the inner surface of the tarpaulin with movement provided by an electric motor (6).

[9] To enable the belt to be tensioned, a tensioner (2) - which consists of an adjustable mass in the longitudinal direction of the treadmill - is fitted with tensioning screws (3) that move this adjustable mass.

[10] The arrangement also features side handles (8) for transporting the equipment, and a system of interchangeable stalls (7) which, when fitted or removed, change the number and dimensions of the available lanes in which the animals are tested.

[11] The stall system (7) is modular and detachable. The apparatus also has an MDF board or similar material that joins the structure transversally and serves as a support for the murines. Finally, a waste scraping plate (5) helps to sanitize the machine.

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[12] The new arrangement has a lifting system (9) for adjusting the inclination of the treadmill in order to increase the intensity of the exercises. For this purpose, the hyperbaric chamber has a fixed end with eyebolts to allow tilting and a linear lifting actuator at the other end, equipped with an electric drive system.

[13] This treadmill is inside a hyperbaric chamber (10) with pressure control, made of translucent material to better visualize the training of the mice, with an upper lid (11) completely sealed off from outside air, except for air vents controlled by an air inlet control device. The lid of this chamber has handles (12) and locking hooks (13) for compression, and a smaller lid (14) for placing mice during exercises without pressure control.

[14] The invention can be better understood with the help of the figures.

[15] Figure 1 shows a perspective view with details of the treadmill.

[16] Figure 2 shows a side view of the new arrangement without a driven lift.

[17] Figure 3 shows a side view of the new layout with the lifting system activated.

[18] Figure 4 shows details of the hyperbaric chamber.

[19] In summary, the new arrangement makes it possible to carry out ergometric tests under various atmospheric pressures, with the possibility of controlling the pressure, speed and inclination of the treadmill inside the chamber, allowing for various variations on physiological tests.

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[20] This invention is not limited to the representations commented on or illustrated here but must be understood in its broad scope. Many modifications and other representations of the innovation will come to the mind of one skilled in the art to which this innovation pertains, having the benefit of the teaching presented in the foregoing descriptions and accompanying drawings. Furthermore, it is to be understood that the innovation is not limited to the specific form disclosed, and that modifications and other forms are understood to be included within the scope of the appended claims. Although specific terms are used herein, they are used only in a generic and descriptive manner and not for the purpose of limitation.

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DEMANDS

1. AUTOMATIC TREADMILL IN HYPERBARIC CHAMBER, **characterized by** comprising a tarpaulin (1), two rollers (4), an electric motor (6), a tensioner (2), an adjusting screw (3), side handles (8), an interchangeable stall system (7), a waste scraping plate (5), a lifting system (9) and a hyperbaric chamber (10).
2. Stall system according to claim 1, **characterized by** being modular and detachable.

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FIGURES

Figure 1

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Figure 2

Figure 3

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Figure 4

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SUMMARY

AUTOMATIC TREADMILL IN HYPERBARIC CHAMBER

Automated treadmills, with speed and incline control, start and end of exercise, specially designed for mice and rats, arranged inside a hyperbaric chamber, in order to carry out ergometric tests, such as walking, running, inclined running, under various atmospheric pressures.

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State of New Jersey.

County of Passaic.

Subscribed and Sworn before me using two-way video and audio this 19 day of

July, 2024. Gabrielle Georges Notary Public
(Notary’s Signature)

Notarized online using audio-video communication

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Commission #: 50217433
Commission Expires: 01/04/2029